

**MICROBIOLOGICAL SURVEILLANCE FOR PETROLEUM -
HYDROCARBON UTILIZERS IN PRODUCED WATER FROM KOKORI,
NIGER - DELTA REGION, NIGERIA**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15517953>

Keywords:

Bioremediation,
Crude oil,
ecosystem,
Hydrocarbon
clastic
microorganisms,
produced water,
sustainable
development

Abstract: The recurrent incidences of accidental release of crude oil and improper disposal of oilfield produced water which is massive into the environment has raised concerns over the adverse effects this may have both on the environment, water conservation and the biota in Niger Delta region. This study aims to isolate, identify and characterize crude oil degrading microorganisms obtained from produced water - polluted environment in Kokori, Niger Delta. The physico-chemical properties of the soil and water samples were determined prior to microbiological and molecular analyses. Three samples were obtained aseptically; bore water, runoff water, and soil samples from a crude oil-contaminated site in Kokori, Niger Delta region at 0 - 30cm depth. The need to give adequate characterization to the microbial populations involved both in biodegradation and bioremediation activities in oil-polluted environment becomes crucial to advance sustainable development and greener ecosystem both nationally and globally. Serial-dilution technique was used to determine the total population of indigenous heterotrophic and crude oil-degrading microorganisms following standard and conventional methods; Nutrient agar, sabouraud dextrose agar and Minimal salt Agar (MSA) supplemented with 0.02% Forcados blend crude oil were used to isolate the microbial populations. These were then incubated at room temperature for 3 and 3-5 days for bacterial as well as fungal isolates respectively. Morphological and biochemical reactions were used initially for the characterization of the isolates.

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Incontrovertible evidence of the identity of these isolates were obtained with the 16S rRNA gene sequencing method. Hydrocarbon-utilizing bacteria isolated included Bacillus pumilus and Bacillus subtilis, the crude oil-degrading fungi isolated were Rhizopus stolonifera, Penicillium roqueforti, and Rhodotorula sp., three hydrocarbonoclastic isolates were randomly selected for molecular characterization following standard procedure. These isolates were Achromobacter insuavis (MK517596.1), Micrococcus endophyticus (MT225734.1), and Aspergillus flavus (LN482496.1). This study successfully identified and characterized crude oil-degrading microorganisms with significant bioremediation potential. These findings highlight the importance of microbial-based solutions in mitigating oil pollution and promoting sustainable environmental restoration as an effort towards a greener ecosystem.

Introduction

Produced water (PW) which is also known as oilfield waste water, is part of the liquid constituent of the petroleum oil reservoirs (Klemz *et al.*, 2020a; Ullattumpoyil, 2023), with the oil/water ratio generally being 1:3, it is slightly acidic and sit below the hydrocarbons in porous reservoir media (Igunnu and Chen, 2014). Produced water is generated in large quantity during oil and gas production process. It is mostly associated with aquifer encroachment and water injection in matured oilfield (Ullattumpoyil, 2023). During petroleum oil recovery, 85-90% of liquid waste is considered as wastewater. It is considered the most important waste stream by volume in the petroleum industry and about 115 billion barrels per year (bbl. /y) of water are produced worldwide as a by-product of oil and gas exploration (Fakhru'l-Razi *et al.*, 2009; Ori-Usifo *et al.*, 2022). Produced water has been reported to have been formed in association with petroleum in shallow arine environments and this by implication accounts for the oil and dissolved salt (mainly NaCl) found in it (Atoufi *et al.*, 2020).

However, histories of subsidence, uplift and reburial, erosion of the oil sedimentary formation can alter the original chemistry of the produced water due to aided meteoric or marine water infiltration. Produce water (PW) are present in equilibrium with the oil and gas incursion within the oil reservoir trapped in the rock and they serve as an excellent solvent that dissolves many of the oil and gas associated compounds. Thus, its composition is very complex (Klemz *et al.*, 2020a, b). Constituents of the complex composition of produced water can be broadly classified into organic and inorganic compounds, including dissolved and dispersed oils (oil in water emulsion), grease, heavy metals, radionuclides, treatment chemicals, formation solids, salts, dissolved gases, scale products, waxes, microorganisms and dissolved oxygen (Danilovic *et al.*, 2016). This water is a mixture of formation water, injection water and small volumes of condensed water from gas production as well as aqueous residues of treatment. Chemicals contained in produced water consists of significant concentration of soluble organic

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compounds including naphthenic acids (NAs), Phenols, aromatic hydrocarbons (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (Leshuk *et al.*, 2016; Ullattumpoyil, 2023). In produced water the total solid concentrations range from as little as 200 ppm to saturation, which is approximately 300,000 ppm. The dissolved cations commonly found are Na^+ , Ca^{++} , and Mg^{++} occasionally K^+ , Ba^{++} , Li^+ , Fe^{++} , and Sr^{++} are present. The most common anions are Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^- . Also, CO_3^{2-} , NO_3^- , Br^- , I^- , BO_3 , and S are often present (Ullattumpoyil, 2023). ^{226}Ra and ^{228}Ra are the most abundant naturally occurring radioactive elements present in oilfield produced water which is as a result of the co-precipitation of radium with barium sulfate scale or any other type of scales (ATSDR, 1999). Produced water have also been recorded to contain microbial life, which is as a result of the marine water infiltration incidents, introducing the marine microbiota into the reservoir during reservoir formation (Su *et al.*, 2022).

Produced water discharge into the environment is associated with negative health and environmental effects due to dissolved pollutants in it, if not properly managed it may cause several environmental impacts that is, change in the chemical, physical or biological properties of the environment which may affect social and economic activities, biota, the health and safety of the population, aesthetics and sanitary conditions or quality of environmental resources (Klemz *et al.*, 2020a,b; Su *et al.*, 2022). The negative impact posed by discharged produced water varies

according to the magnitude of its “environmental impact factor” which are its temperature, high salinity, the presence of suspended solids, heavy metals, soluble organic compounds, chemicals and radioactivity (Klemz *et al.*, 2020b; Su *et al.*, 2022). Another significant problem of produced water in petroleum industry is the occurrence of limescale, saturation of the produced water by any of the ions (Klemz *et al.*, 2020b) or Change in the pressure and temperature of ground water when entering to the borehole which leads to a sudden deposition of CaCO_3 ↓ due to release of CO_2 ↑ and decrease in pH, which can lead to clogging of the oil production filters, accelerated consumption of injection pipes and the creation of local corrosive surface (Isek *et al.*, 2018). Produced water is most often considered a waste, but industries are beginning to consider this material as a potential profit stream (Eyitayo, 2023) as it can be reused for various industrial application, for irrigation, wildlife consumption, industrial water and even drinking water (Eyitayo *et al.*, 2023). Beyond the primary use of produce water and the environmental threat it poses as a pollutant, paradoxically it also contains microbial entities capable of facilitating the process of bioremediation and can also serve a critical role in microbiological enhanced oil recovery process (MEOR) (Gao *et al.*, 2014).

The annual estimates of PW in the United States were around 890 billion gallons (3.37 billion m^3), thus making it the largest waste stream associated with oil and gas activities (Veil, 2020). The volume of PW generated tends to increase on a yearly basis as old fields mature and as new oil

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fields emerge (Khatib and Verbeek, 2003) and these can be attributed to the expansion of unconventional oil and gas development, which produced more than 50% of crude oil and natural gas in recent times (U.S.EIA, 2020). Produced waters are characterized by a high content of salt and oil that necessitates specific treatment train in order to decontaminate them, as for example with respect to municipal wastewater. Typically, produced water contains high concentrations of aromatic hydrocarbons e.g BTEX (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene), NP (naphthalene, phenanthrene e dibenzothiophene) and PAH (polycyclic aromatic compounds), minerals, radioactive substances, dissolved gasses, scale products, waxes, microorganisms and dissolved oxygen (Su *et al.*, 2022).

In the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, which is known for its oil reservoirs and a hotspot for crude oil exploration companies, over the years have experienced a lot of negative impact from crude oil exploration and exploitation activities such as gas flaring which pollutes the air, poor maintenances of oil wells contamination of both surface and ground waters, and operational accidents which could also lead to pollution of the surrounding soil and aquatic habitat. In a population that depends on crude farming, fishing, logging and hunting for a living, such an impact could result into starvation as well as poverty and by implication severe economic losses, social inequalities and even jeopardize the 2030 agenda on sustainable development (Olalekhan *et al.*, 2022). Considering the biological approach of remediating polluted

environment, it is not the most efficient, but cost effective and environment - friendly, capitalizing on the metabolism, metabolites, physical activities (active efflux), and natural abundance of microorganisms. Although, physical and chemical methods of remediating polluted environment exist with promising results, paradoxically they are not cost - effective and often times generate harmful by - product into the environment (Olalekhan *et al.*, 2022).

Crude oil spills are significant environmental hazards, primarily caused by equipment failures, operational mistakes, and leaks from outdated pipes or intentional damage. While these are the most commonly reported incidents, other contributing factors include petroleum exploration and exploitation activities, with rare instances of natural crude oil seepages (Nwaichi and Wegwu, 2015). Several scientists and environmental microbiologists have described the use of plant, algae, bacteria and fungi in bioremediation of crude oil - contaminated site (Ite and Ibok, 2019). Apart from yeasts of the genera *Candida* (*C. lipolytica*, *C. tropicalis*), *Hansenula*, *Torulopsis*, *Rhodotorula* and fungi from the genera *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, and *Trichoderma*, while bacteria, including species from the genera *Pseudomonas*, *Vibrio*, *Arthrobacter*, *Aeromonas*, *Acinetobacter* are significant and active participant in the degradation of petroleum hydrocarbon (Ojo-Omoniyi *et al.*, 2018). Over the years, bioremediation has proven to be a cost-effective and environment-friendly approach compared to physico-chemical techniques, which requires

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expensive chemicals, high energy input, and sophisticated technology (Eyitayo *et al.*, 2023). Compared to physic-chemical methods, bioremediation is a more suitable option for treating contaminated soil and groundwater, as it does not lead to further contamination (Biocanin *et al.*, 2015). A substantial body of scientific research has documented the potential of various micro- and macro-organisms to degrade oil in contaminated environments, primarily soil. Several fungal, plant, and algal species, alongside a diverse range of bacteria, have been identified as capable of directly or indirectly metabolizing hydrocarbons as a source of both energy and carbon. Bacteria isolated from polluted soil known to utilize hydrocarbons (HUB) include *Bacillus* sp., *Micrococcus* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Acinetobacter* sp., *Flavobacterium* sp., and *Alcaligenes* sp. Fungal genera documented to possess hydrocarbon-degradation capabilities include *Penicillium* sp., *Aspergillus* sp., and *Fusarium* sp. (Onuoha *et al.*, 2023). Recent studies estimated that over 79 bacterial genera are implicated in the degradation of petroleum hydrocarbons. Among these, *Achromobacter*, *Acinetobacter*, *Alkanindiges*, *Alteromonas*, *Arthrobacter*, *Burkholderia*, *Dietzia*, *Enterobacter*, *Kocuria*, *Marinobacter*, *Mycobacterium*, *Pandoraea*, *Pseudomonas*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptobacillus*, *Streptococcus*, and *Rhodococcus* are the most frequently encountered genera known to play a critical role in this process (Xu *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, specific species within these genera have been classified as obligate hydrocarbonoclastic

bacteria, meaning they rely solely on hydrocarbons for growth. Examples of obligate hydrocarbonoclastic bacteria include; *Alcanivorax*, *Marinobacter*, *Thalassolituus*, *Cycloclasticus*, and *Oleispira* (Vural, 2022). *Alcaligenes borkumensis*, a well-studied example of a hydrocarbonoclastic bacterium, exhibits a remarkable capacity to degrade a wide range of hydrocarbons. These include alkanes, branched-aliphatic hydrocarbons, isoprenoid hydrocarbons and alkylcycloalkanes (Vural, 2022). Fungi play a significant role in the bioremediation of contaminated environments by degrading recalcitrant polar hydrocarbons, such as asphaltene and resins. This degradation process can be mediated by enzymatic and/or non-enzymatic reactions employed by these microorganisms (Vural, 2022). Aerobic bacteria are often isolated from produced water samples, suggesting they are exogenous contaminants introduced during drilling or well operations (Nazina *et al.*, 2020a; Eyitayo *et al.*, 2023). *Ochrobactrum*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Brevundimonas* are common aerobic organotrophic bacteria, meaning they require oxygen and organic matter for growth. Studies on Russian heavy oil reservoirs revealed the presence of another group of aerobic bacteria (Nazina *et al.*, 2020a). These bacteria, belonging to the genera; *Rhodococcus*, *Gordonia*, *Nocardia*, *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* have shown surprising ability to produce biosurfactants on various substrates and even in the presence of crude oil, suggesting their potential role in enhancing oil mobilization and bioremediation (Nazina *et al.*, 2020a).

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Biodegradation of petroleum hydrocarbons by bacteria involves a series of coordinated processes. These processes enable bacteria to transform complex organic compounds into simpler, more readily utilizable forms. This synergy allows them to collaborate and degrade complex compounds more efficiently as a consortium, some bacteria possess the remarkable ability to detoxify harmful substances during biodegradation. They can transform or degrade these toxic compounds into less hazardous forms, thereby mitigating the environmental impact of the pollutants (Olalekhan *et al.*, 2022; Eyitayo *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2025). Microbial communities exhibit remarkable versatility in their ability to degrade petrochemicals. Different bacterial genera preferentially target specific types of hydrocarbons for degradation. Furthermore, these bacteria can function under both aerobic and anaerobic conditions (Eyitayo *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2025). Several bacterial genera, including *Desulfococcus*, *Thauera*, *Dechloromonas*, and *Azoarcus*, harbor species known for their ability to degrade hydrocarbons under anaerobic conditions (Eyitayo *et al.*, 2023). The objectives of the current study are to isolate, identify and characterize autochthonous crude oil degraders obtained from produced water from crude oil mining environment at Kokori, Niger Delta.

Materials and Methods

Study area

Kokori is a town located in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, specifically in Ethiope East Local

Government Area (LGA), Delta State. It is part of the Agbon Kingdom and is known for its rich oil reserves. Despite its oil wealth, Kokori faces significant challenges, including poverty and neglect. The town has over twenty oil wells and produces high-quality crude oil with low Sulphur content. However, the benefits of this natural resource have not translated into meaningful development for the local community. Residents often deal with poor infrastructure, lack of basic amenities, and environmental pollution caused by oil exploration. Samples used during the course of this project work was collected from Kokori, Niger Delta, located in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, with approximate coordinates of 5.55° N latitude and 6.00° E longitude.

Sample collection

Waterlogged soil and water sample were collected from Kokori, Niger Delta area. The sample was collected at a depth of 0-30cm with a sterile trowel. The collected soil sample was kept in a sterile plastic bottle container and with proper labelling. It was transported to the laboratory and stored in the refrigerator at 4°C until they were used. The research was carried out at Microbiology laboratory, Lagos state University, Ojo.

Determination of physic - chemical properties of water and soil samples

The soil and water samples were taken to the laboratory for proximate analysis following the methods of Bareither *et al.* (2010).

Microbiological analysis

Serial dilution technique was used as described by Gerhardt *et al.* (1981), with the spread plate

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method. Approximately, 0.1 mL aliquot sample of the 10^{-4} dilution of both soil and water samples was inoculated aseptically into the nutrient medium, sabouraud dextrose medium and minimal salt medium (MSM) supplemented with 0.02% Forcados blend crude oil in duplicates, so as to enumerate the total heterotrophic bacterial and fungal populations as well as crude oil – degraders respectively. The nutrient agar (NA) was incubated for 24 hours, Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) plates were incubated for 3-5 days, while the minimal salt medium supplemented with crude oil was incubated for 7-10 days at room temperature ($26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), this was done through vapour-phase transfer (Amund and Igiri, 1990; Raymond *et al.*, 1976; Okerentugba and Ezeronye, 2003). The sabouraud dextrose agar plate fortified with 0.5ml of chloramphenicol to prevent bacteria growth to which crude oil was fed using crude oil-soaked sterile filter paper in vapour - phase transfer technique.

Media preparation

The media used include: Nutrient agar (HiMedia, India), Sabouraud dextrose agar (HiMedia, India), SIMS media (Thermofisher scientific, USA) and Minimal salt medium; was used as an enrichment culture as described by kohler *et al.* (1987) and Buraimoh *et al.* (2017). The media contains the following constituents in g/L of distilled water; KH_2PO_4 2.7g, Na_2HPO_4 2.8g, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ 0.3g, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.5g, $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ 0.1g. Trace element solution 0.25ml and Agar 20g, the pH of the media was adjusted to 7.2 before autoclaving (Searchtech instrument, British standard), for 15 minutes. All media were

prepared according to the manufacturer's instruction (Acharya, 2023) and were all sterilized at 121°C for 15 minutes.

Morphological and biochemical characterization of microbial isolates

All isolates were examined and characterized using standard and conventional methods. The bacteria isolates were observed under the microscope using $\times 100$ objective lenses. Pure Fungal cultures were observed while still on plates and after wet mount in lacto-phenol blue on slides under the binocular microscope $\times 40$ objective lenses (Olympus Japan). The observed characteristics were recorded and compared with the established identification keys of Gerhardt *et al.*, (1981) and Smith, (1981).

The biochemical tests used for characterization of isolates includes; Gram staining, catalase test, Indole test, Oxidase test, Motility test, hydrogen sulfide production

DNA extraction and amplification of the I6S rRNA gene

DNA extraction

A measurement of 80mg (wet weight) of bacterial cell that had been re-suspended in up to $200\mu\text{l}$ of deionized water to a ZR BashingBead™ Lysis Tube was obtained. It was secure in a bead beater fitted with a 2.0ml tube holder assembly (Scientific Industries' Disruptor Genie™, Cat. No. S6001-2 from Zymo Research Corp.) and processed at maximum speed for 5 minutes. The ZR BashingBead™ Lysis Tube was centrifuged in a micro-centrifuge at $\geq 10,000 \times g$ for 1minute. Up to $400\mu\text{l}$ supernatant was transferred to a Zymo-Spin™ IV Spin Filter (orange top) in a Collection

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Tube and centrifuged at 7,000 rpm (7,000 x g) for 1 minute. The base of the Zymo-Spin™ IV Spin Filter was snapped off prior to use. 1,200µl of Bacterial DNA Binding Buffer was added to the filtrate in the collection tube of step four. Thereafter, 800µl of the mixture from step five was transferred to a Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column in a Collection Tube and centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 1minute. The flow through was discarded from the Collection Tube and step six was repeated. Then, 200µl DNA Per-Wash Buffer was added to the Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column in a new Collection Tube and centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 1minute. Thereafter, 500µl Fungal DNA Wash Buffer was added to the Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column and centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 1minute. The Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column was transferred to a clean 1.5ml micro-centrifuge tube and 100µl DNA Elution Buffer was added directly to the column matrix. It was then centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 30seconds to elute the DNA. The bacterial DNA were extracted following Zymo research protocols (Guter & Koshland Jr. 1990; Kamusoko *et al.*, 2021; Qiagen, 2016).

PCR Amplification of the ITS/16S rRNA Gene and Sequencing

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was carried out to amplify the ITS gene of the fungal isolates using the primer pair ITS-1 (5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG-3') and ITS-4 (5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3'). The PCR reaction was carried out using the Solis Biodyne 5× HOT FIREPol Blend Master mix. The bacterial isolates 16S rRNA gene was amplified following the protocols of Qiagen (Qiagen, 2016).

PCR was performed in 25 µl of a reaction mixture, and the reaction concentration was brought down from 5× concentration to 1× concentration containing 1× Blend Master mix buffer Buffer (Solis Biodyne), 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 200µM of each deoxynucleoside triphosphates (dNTP)(Solis Biodyne), 25pMol of each primer (BIOMERS, Germany) and 2 unit of Hot FIREPol DNA polymerase (Solis Biodyne). Additional Taq DNA polymerase was incorporated into the reaction mixture to make a final concentration of 2.5 units of Taq DNA polymerase, Proof reading Enzyme, 2µl of the extracted DNA, and sterile distilled water was used to make up the reaction mixture. Thermal cycling was conducted in an Eppendorf Vapo protect thermal cycler (Nexus Series U.S.A.) for an initial denaturation of 95°C for 15 minutes followed by 35 amplification cycles of 30 seconds at 95°C; 1 minute at 58°C and 1 minute 30 Seconds at 72°C. This was followed by a final extension step of 10 minutes at 72°C. (Guter & Koshland Jr. 1990; Solanki, 2012; Kamusoko *et al.*, 2021).

16S rRNA / ITS Analysis:

PCR amplification of the 16S rRNA gene was performed using the following primers:

Forward Primer (with T7 tail):

TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGTTTGATCC
TGGCTCAG

Reverse Primer: GYTACCTTGTTACGACTT

PCR amplification of the ITS gene was performed using the following primers:

Forward primer (ITS1):
TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG

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Reverse primer (ITS4):
TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC

PCR is performed using the amplification program:

96°C (5 min), followed by 30 cycles of 96°C (15 sec.), 52°C (15 sec.), 72°C (90 sec.).

PCR completed with 5 min incubation at 72°C. Approximately, 5µl aliquot from each PCR reaction was run on 1% TAE Agarose gel to confirm positive PCR outcome. PCR products were treated with ExoSAP and sequenced (Sanger Sequencing) (Guter and Koshland Jr. 1990; Qiagen, 2016).

The sequence information was analyzed using National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) Blast.

(https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi?PAGE_TYPE=BlastSearch)

Sequencing

The extracted DNA was subjected to amplification with a thermal cycler (Helena Biosciences, Sunderland, United Kingdom) and the primers listed in Table 3 were used. All the primers, synthesized by Sigma Aldrich House, Suffolk, United Kingdom, were used in four sets of PCR procedures (Qiagen, 2016; Kamusoko *et al.*, 2021).

Analysis

In order to identify organisms, DNA sequence data generated from this study was blasted against

ITS/16S rRNA type strain database on NCBI. Threshold for identification was set according to Wang *et al.* (2014) with modification to accommodate species with high congeneric

sequence divergence range. Phylogeny was constructed to support the identification by ITS sequence using Fast Minimum Evolution algorithm as deployed on NCBI and visualized on MEGA11 (Tamura *et al.*, 2021). In the estimation of genus diversity, as opposed to the treatment in the estimation of species diversity, unidentified isolates were removed from the analysis. Other descriptive and inferential statistics were carried out in R using the following R packages: base (R. Core Team, 2021), reshape2 (Wickham, 2007), dplyr (Wickham *et al.*, 2021), ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), ggpubr (Kassambara, 2020), qpcR (Spiess, 2018), knitr (Xie, 2014; Xie, 2015; Xie, 2021). Data wrangling was achieved using Reshape2 and dplyr, inferential statistics were carried out in R, and data were visualized using ggplot2, ggpubr, qpcR, and knitr.

Results

The critical analysis of the data obtained from Kokori town evidenced that it has rich oil reserves with many oil wells and it has high quality crude oil with low Sulphur content. However, surprisingly the mean pH values of the composite soil sample (7.05) were almost neutral while the composite sample of the runoff water and bore water were slightly acidic (6.27 and 6.45 respectively). this neutral pH is conducive to the growth and metabolic activities of a wide range of microorganisms, including those capable of degrading hydrocarbons. The Total Organic Carbon (TOC) value of 2.73 in the soil sample indicated a nutrient-rich environment, which is essential for sustaining microbial populations in crude oil- polluted environment.

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The crude oil exploration site had no agricultural activity ongoing since its water logged. However, a reasonable distance (300m) from the exploration point agricultural activities were observable which might have significantly influenced the mean pH readings from the location (Table 1). Total organic C (TOC) was low in both runoff water and bore water (0.036 and 0.035 respectively), while in contrast the soil TOC was relatively low which suggested low soil fertility at this location. The nitrate (NO₃⁻¹) concentration was highest in the runoff water (20.34mg/L), this suggested that most of the organic C and N were being washed by the volume of waste water from the exploration site. Although, only Pb was analyzed of all metals but its concentration (<0.001mg/L) in all the samples was insignificant (Table1). The fact that other minerals in the soil were being washed away by the high volume of produced water generated

from the mining site to nearby farmlands was authenticated by the higher concentrations of Ca²⁺, Na⁺, K⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions detectable in the soil further away from the oil wells. The terrain of the oil well is water logged thus not accessible but by automated machines. Cation exchange coefficient (C.E.C.) attested to the fact that biogeochemical activities were taking place in the environment mediated primarily by microbial communities (Table 1). The mean temperature of 28±2°C of both bore water and runoff water was due to impact of nearby freshwater river and water-logged landmass. The physicochemical analysis of soil and water samples from Kokori, Niger Delta region, provides crucial insights into the synergy among indigenous microbial communities deploring their metabolic capacity at utilizing crude oil for energy and biomass production. The suitability for bioremediation and the population dynamics of crude oil-degrading microorganisms.

Table 1: Mean values of physic-chemical properties of the composite soil and water samples.

Parameters	Kokori soil	Kokori runoff water	Kokori Bore water
Ph	7.05	6.27	6.45
TOC (mg/L)	2.73	0.036	0.035
NO ₃ (mg/L)	19.41	20.34	14.53
Pb (mg/L)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Ca (mg/L)	682.321	0.288	0.635
K (mg/L)	127.688	17.854	0.274

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Mg (mg/L)	87.809	3.024	0.019
Na (mg/L)	170.555	67.640	22.668
CEC, meq/100g	5.212	0.367	0.103
Temperature (°C)	28±2	30±2	26

Key:

THC: Total Heterotrophic Bacteria Count (Cfu/mL) × 10⁴ Dilution Factor

THB: Total bacterial crude oil- Degraders

Fig. 1: Total Heterotrophic Bacteria Count and Total bacterial petroleum-hydrocarbon Degraders.

Key:

THC: Total Heterotrophic Fungal Count (Cfu/mL) × 10⁴ Dilution Factor

THF: Total Fungal Petroleum-hydrocarbon utilizers

Fig. 2: Total heterotrophic fungal count and Total fungal hydrocarbon degraders

Table 2: Morphological characterization of bacterial crude oil-degraders

Isolate Code	Probable bacteria	Colonial morphology	Microscopic characterization
A1	<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	Yellow colony, smooth, circular, raised and shiny	Rod and clustered
A2	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Cream and large colony, rough surface, irregular edges and glistening appearance.	Short rod, in pairs and (diplo), with sub-terminal endospore.
A3	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Bright yellow, shiny, raised, circular	Cocci and clustered

A4	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	White, smooth, circular, raised and shiny	Cocci and clustered
A5	<i>Bacillus species</i>	Cream, smooth surface, irregular growth pattern, glistening and domed	Short rod clustered
A6	<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	Bright orange, smooth, shiny, concentric ring pattern and circular	Short rod and clustered, presence of terminal endospore
A7	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Cream, undulate edge, raised, and circular.	Short rod and clustered, presence of terminal endospore.

Crude oil degrading bacterial isolated from the sample were identified as *Bacillus pumilus* (A6) and *Bacillus subtilis* (A7).

Table 3: Morphological and biochemical characterization of Heterotrophic bacterial isolates

Isolate	Colony Morphology	Cell Shape	Gram Reaction	Indole	Urease	Voges-Proskauer	Catalase	Methyl Red	Citrate	Oxidase	Gelatin Hydrolysis	Probable Organism
H1w	Creamy edge	rods	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
H2w	Whitish edge sliming.	Short rod curvy	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	<i>Corynebacterium sp.</i>
H3w	Thin colonies, scanty.	Rod	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>
H4w	Tiny greenish	Rod	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>

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H5 _s	Creamy, slime	Long rod	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	<i>Aeromonas sp.</i>
H6 _s	Creamy	Short rod	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
H7 _s	Round convex	Rod	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>

Table 4: Morphological characterization of hydrocarbon- utilizing fungal isolates

Isolates code	Probable fungi	Colonial morphology	Microscopic identification
D3	<i>Rhodotorula species</i>	Coral-like, light pink, branching growth pattern.	complex Sclerotium mass, with ovalate sclerotium cells
B3	<i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i>	Compartmentalized polygonal zones, dense and cottony with powdery surface	Simple, erect, hyaline sporangiospores, bearing a colluminate sporangia. The sporangia white outer edges and greenish black and globose. Hyaline coloured center of the compartment. Sporangiospore that has an ellipsoidal shape.
B2	<i>Aspergillus versicolor</i>	Compact, segmented appearance with a central point of growth, forming radial, circular pattern. It has a bluish-green center with white edges. Presence of red-brown droplet/exudate.	Curved conidiospore, with apical globose vesicle bearing uniseriate phialides bearing conidia. Conidia are phialisporous, hyaline and ellipsoidal.
D1	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Fluffy, and powdery surface, compact appearance with a central greenish mycelia, and a white radial edges.	Large Broad, simple, erect and hyaline conidiospore with a clavate or globose apical vesicle bearing uniseriate phialides. Conidio phialosporous, ellipsoidal, hyaline conidia.

C2	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Fluffy surface, Large compact appearance with a black to brown transition at the center (mycelia), and a white radial edge	Conidiophore; hyaline, simple, erect, thick walled, inflated at the apex forming globose vesicles bearing conidia. Heads split into over 4 loose conidial columns composed of catenulate conidia borne on uniseriate phialides, conidiophialosporous, are black, brown in mass, globose, minutely echinulate.
C1	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	Velvety appearance, Compact, segmented appearance with a central point of growth, forming radial, circular pattern. It has a dark center with white edges.	Simple, erect, septate and hyaline conidiophore branching penicillately at the apex with terminal verticillate phialides. Conidia; conidiophialosporous, catenulate conidia.
D2	<i>Penicillium roqueforti</i>	Cottony and fluffy appearance with a powdery surface, compact and circular colony with a greenish center and white edges	Simple, erect, septate and hyaline conidiophore branching penicillately at the apex with terminal verticillate phialides. Conidia; conidiophialosporous, catenulate conidia
B1	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	Compact and segmented appearance, with a large blue center and relatively little peripheral white edges.	Broad, simple, erect, smooth and hyaline conidiophore bearing a globose vesicle with dark conidia attached to the vesicle.

Crude oil degrading fungi isolated from the sample were identified as *Rhodotorula* species (D3), *Penicillium roqueforti* (D2), and *Rhizopus stolonifera* (B3)

Table 5: Molecular identification of bacterial crude oil degraders

ISOLATE CODE	SCIENTIFIC NAME	ACCESSION NUMBER
BXW	<i>Achromobacter insuavis</i>	MK517596.1
B1W	<i>Micrococcus endophticus</i>	MT225734.1

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ASA

Aspergillus flavus

LN482496.1

The heterotrophic bacterial count was more (15.0 - 30.0×10⁴Cfu/mL) than that of the petroleum-hydrocarbon utilizers that range from approximately 5.0 - 12.0 ×10⁴ Cfu/mL on microbiological media (Fig.1). The heterotrophic fungal population were more in bore water (3.0×10⁴Cfu/mL) than those of runoff water (2.0×10⁴Cfu/mL) and composite soil sample (2.0×10⁴Cfu/mL) (Fig.2). This suggested that despite operating in an acidophilic environment there were more bacterial-mediated biogeochemical processes in Kokori mining site than fungal-mediated activities (Fig. 2). The morphological and biochemical analysis revealed the characteristics of microbial communities that formed the crude oil-degrader consortium at the oil exploration point at Kokori (Table 3 and 4). Further investigation led to engagement of 16S rRNA molecular method and gene sequencing to give incontrovertible identities of crude oil-degraders at the site (Table 5).

Discussion

The presence of both bacterial and fungal population as mixed culture from the studied microcosm, indicated that no single organism has the metabolic capability to mineralize the complex petroleum hydrocarbons but as a consortium. The runoff and bore water samples had slightly lower pH values of 6.27 and 6.45, respectively, which has non-significant influence on microbial growth in the soil. However, there were indigenous acidophilic microbial populations in the investigated oil mining site,

this corroborated the report of Francioli *et al.* (2016) that nutrient availability is crucial for microbial proliferation than favorable pH, since the hydrocarbonoclastic microbial communities in the Niger Delta region were found to be synergistic in nutrient cycling as well as having dynamic metabolic systems to mitigate adverse environmental factors in such a manner that both biodegradation and bioremediation simultaneously took place in the oil - contaminated environment. . Liu *et al.* (2021) reported that high TOC levels support microbial growth and efficient biogeochemical activities in the ecosystem. The findings in this study *were* further corroborated by the submissions of Olaniyan *et al.* (2022) that *reiterated* that these nutrients *were* critical for microbial growth and activity, *thus* enhancing the soil's potential for bioremediation. Williams and Thompson (2021) observed that natural attenuation processes in runoff can aid in hydrocarbon degradation. This is consistent with the findings of Atlas (2008), who reported that runoff can carry hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria from contaminated areas to unpolluted environment when the prevailing physico-chemical factors are similar in the ecosystems. The hydrocarbonoclastic microbial populations included *Micrococcus luteus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Bacillus* sp. and *Bacillus subtilis* using conventional cultural methods. However, 16S rRNA method characterized these crude oil-degrading bacterial species as

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Bacillus pumilus and *Bacillus subtilis*. This aligns with the previous submissions by other scientists (Das and Chandran, 2011; Ojo-Omoniyi *et al.*, 2018). The hydrocarbon-utilizing fungi identified from the samples include *Rhodotorula* sp., *Rhizopus stolonifera* and *Penicillium roqueforti*. The 16S rRNA gene sequencing method identified *Achromobacter insuavis*, *Micrococcus endophyticus*, and *Aspergillus flavus* as crude oil degraders and this substantiated their potential as a cheap natural resource for bioremediation of hydrocarbon-contaminated environments. These microorganisms have been identified through various molecular techniques, including 16S rRNA gene sequencing for bacteria and ITS region sequencing for fungi, which confirmed their taxonomic positions and capabilities in hydrocarbon degradation. This is consistent with the findings of Xu *et al.* (2018), who reported that *Achromobacter insuavis* possesses genes encoding enzymes crucial for hydrocarbon degradation. The work of Ojo-Omoniyi *et al.* (2018) confirmed that *Aspergillus flavus* has robust hydrocarbon - degrading abilities due to its metabolic capacity to synthesize relevant enzymes. Total Heterotrophic Bacterial Count (THBC) and Total Hydrocarbon Degrading Bacteria (THB) count, as observed in the study. Previous studies by Fierer and Jackson (2006) have shown that nutrient-rich environments promote the proliferation of diverse microbial communities, including those capable of degrading hydrocarbons, this is in agreement with our findings at Kokori and this is corroborated by Olalekhan *et al.* (2022).

Bioaugmentation of PW- polluted environment with selected microbial species, would offer an effective strategy for the bioremediation of petroleum-contaminated soils as well as enhance sustainable agricultural activities, this has also been suggested by Wang *et al.* (2025).

Conclusion

Microorganisms remain the key players in the race to restoring polluted lands and relieving the environment of toxic and mutagenic components. The physicochemical properties of the soil and water samples significantly influence the microbial populations and activity of crude oil-degrading microorganisms. The soil sample, with its favorable pH and higher organic matter content, provides a more suitable environment for bioremediation as well as agricultural activities. The runoff water, bore water and soil supported microbial activities that led to utilization of petroleum - hydrocarbons in the contaminated environment. Future studies should focus on optimizing the conditions for microbial growth and exploring the use of hydrocarbonoclastic microbes to enhance bioremediation efficiency. This study highlights the significant potential of *Achromobacter insuavis*, *Micrococcus endophyticus*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Bacillus pumilus*, and *Bacillus subtilis* in the bioremediation of hydrocarbon-contaminated ecosystem as well as enhanced green ecosystem.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to Dr. Ola-Gbadamosi and Mr. Olusola Tijani, Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, Lagos State University, Lagos – Nigeria, for their technical assistance. We are

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also grateful to Mr. Ogheneyoma Paul Oruero for facilitating sample collection.

Statements and declarations

Funding: The authors declare that no funds, grants or other support were received during the preparation of this manuscript. This is self-funded research by the listed Authors.

Competing interests: The authors have no competing interest to disclose because this study was self-sponsored by all the listed authors as a collaborative study. The authors did not receive support from any organization for the conduct of the study and the submitted manuscript.

Author contributions: The study was conceptualized, designed and preparations by Ojo-Omoniyi, O. A., while data collections, analysis and editing were made by Mr. Q. O. Jamiu, Miss. F. O. Rufai, Mr. A. O. Kuye, Mr. H.O.

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Bello and Mr. A.S. Akinola. All authors contributed equally in the editing of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Dataset: All Dataset are available in GenBank and NCBI repository, the Accession numbers for isolates are displayed and trackable. (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome).

Ethical consent: Ethical approval is not required for this type of work in Nigeria, since we did not test any material on human and animal subjects.

Consent to Participate: The consent to participate in this study was given by each author.

Consent to Publish: The consent of each author was obtained prior to the commencement of the publishing process.

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